

The impact of a flavanol-based biostimulant on plants grown on substrates composed of peat, compost and biochar

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During the last years, the use of biochar or compost as substitutes for peat in horticulture has gained interest [1]. However, there are still knowledge gaps on the effect of these substitutes on plant growing parameters. Bearing in mind the increasing costs of fertilizers, especially for N and P and the need of reducing the use of pesticides, have encouraged the and the application of bio-stimulant products, among others, for sustainable agriculture. In this work, we studied the suitability of biochar, peat and compost mixtures as plant growing substrates for lettuce growth (*Lactuca sativa*) and tested the impact of an flavanol-based biostimulant on plant performance in a greenhouse pot experiment for 40 days. The substrate mixtures (peat:biochar:compost:vermiculite) were as follows: 70:0:0:30 (PB0), 40:5:25:30 (PB5), 0:0:70:30 (CB0); 0:15:55:30 (CB15), 0:30:40:30 (CB30) and 0:50:20:30 (CB50). Organic substrate mixtures were characterized by elemental and chemical parameters and ¹³C-CPMAS NMR spectroscopy at the beginning and end of plant bioassay. Plant parameters studied clustered germination, plant growth, plant physiological traits and diverse antioxidant capacity assays. Our results show that the partial replacement of peat for biochar and compost together with bio-stimulant application represents a good alternative to promote organic sustainable horticulture.

References:

[1] García-Rodríguez, Á. F., Moreno-Racero, F. J., García de Castro Barragán, J. M., Colmenero-Flores, J. M., Greggio, N., Knicker, H., & Rosales, M. A. (2022). Influence of Biochar Mixed into Peat Substrate on Lettuce Growth and Nutrient Supply. *Horticulturae*, 8(12), 1214.

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